

Interoperable geographically distributed astronomical infrastructures: technical solutions.

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In a joint project between the Canadian Advanced Network for Astronomical Research (CANFAR) and the INAF-Osservatorio Astronomico di Trieste (OATs), partially funded by the EGI-Engage H2020 European Project, we deployed at INAF-OATs an astronomical infrastructure mainly based on a set of open-source APIs, made available by CADC (Canadian Astronomical Data Center), implementing a set of IVOA standards and recommendations. This work is relevant to cloud interoperability using VO standards, and is being contributed to WP3 (OBELICS) of the ASTERICS project.

In this poster we describe technical problems faced, specifically we show the designing, technological and architectural solutions adopted for the authorization, authentication and data sharing. We depict our technological overall solution to bring data close to computation resources. Besides the adopted solutions, we propose some points for an open discussion on authentication and authorization mechanisms.

VOSpace Service

"VOSpace, Version 2.1" IVOA recommendation says: "A VOSpace web service is an access point for a distributed storage network. Through this access point, a client can:

- add or delete data objects
 - manipulate metadata for the data object
 - obtain URIs through which the content of the data objects can be accessed
- VOSpace does not define how the data is stored or transferred, but only the control messages to gain access. Thus, the VOSpace interface can readily be added to an existing storage system."

A storage service based on the VOSpace IVOA allowing users to access, process and share their data needs to implement the IVOA recommendation but also a data transfer service interfacing with a storage solution.

- A storage service implementation can be split in three main components:
- **VOSpace interface**, called VOSpace front-end, responsible of the meta-data management;
- **data transfer service**, responsible for handling the information on how to upload and download data;
- **vospace-backend**, is a storage service management to connect a VOSpace interface implementation with a specific storage solution. It manages the physical storage layer and points to the data locations.

VOSpace interface

IVOA VOSpace recommendation 2.1 implementation

Java RESTful web service

Meta-data persistence of stored files in a configurable relational database. Mysql, MariaDB, Sybase and Postgres tested and used in different environments (testing and production).

Defines the software interface with the transfer service to acquire transfer details in the transfer negotiation process, called TransferGenerator.

Transfer service

Implements the TransferGenerator interface giving information needed to store and retrieve physical data to and from the configured VOSpace back-end.

VOSpace Backend

The vospace-backend is a storage service management to be queried by a VOSpace interface to access physical data locations.

- * Persists the information linking a VOSpace Node Identifier with a VOSpace back-end stored file, so it is able to return URIs to access the content of the data objects.
- * A SQL Resource DataBase Management Service (RDBMS) is the default built-in persistence layer.
- * Plug-in architecture to manage at run time different storage solutions. Available plug-ins:
 - ✓ **posix** file system storage
 - ✓ **OpenStack swift** storage
- The selected plug-in has to be indicated in a configuration file.
- * RESTful interface [queried by the front-end to store and retrieve data].

Authentication, authorization and interoperability

Access control

RESTful service management of groups and users, user authentication, authorization checks by group membership.

Authentication

Users may have multiple identities Authentication means recognize one identity (X.509 certificate, user/password, cookies)

Authorization

A resource is protected assigning (granting) access to a group. Done by resource owner. Users can be members, administrators, or owners of groups. Users are authorized to a resource (e.g. a service or proprietary data) if they are a member of the group(s) protecting that resource.

Interoperability

Granted by the use of X.509 personal certificates. CANFAR and OATs-INAF infrastructures, maintain almost three identities of a registered user: the numeric identity (for internal purpose), a username/password identity, a X.509 certificate identity. EGI supports X.509 authentication and authorization through VOMS and Keystone-VOMS module. A VOMS proxy certificate allows access to EGI service at OATs-INAF and IVOA based services at OATs-INAF and CANFAR.

Links:

- www.ivoa.net
- <http://wiki.ivoa.net/internal/IVOA/InteropOct2015GWS/InteroperableAA.pdf>

- <https://github.com/opencadc>
- <https://github.com/oats-cadc>
- <https://github.com/opencadc>
- <https://gms01.oats.inaf.it/doc/index.html>

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